

Building the role of ICT coordinators in primary schools. A typology based on task prioritization

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Building the role of ICT coordinators in primary schools. A typology based on task prioritization

Peer review only

Practitioner Notes

What is already known about this topic

Reports and scientific papers highlight the importance of the ICT coordinator's role when dynamizing the integration of ICTs in schools.

Education authorities, aware of the importance of this role, have promoted its implementation in schools.

The institutionalized role definition does not guarantee that ICT coordinators adjust their role to the said functions.

What this paper adds

We will study the role orientation of ICT coordinators by analyzing how they individually prioritize their functions.

The cluster dendrogram suggested that there were three different types of role orientation in ICT coordinators.

The majority cluster, formed by two out of three coordinators, prioritized classroom activities and simple tasks.

Around 85% of ICT coordinators focused their role on developing ICT classroom activities.

Implications for practice and/or policy

More focus should be given to training and motivating ICT coordinators so that his role orientation does not go against the shared vision the school.

The need to separate technological from pedagogical functions involves a role conflict for ICT coordinators.

Educational Administrations, through the teachers' centers, should offer more support and develop new training opportunities to improve the planning skills of the ICT coordinators.

Abstract

Although the school ICT coordinator's role has been institutionally defined, individual factors could be key in the emerging role-building process. Multidimensional scaling of the priority given by coordinators to their different functions and a subsequent cluster analysis of the MDS solution were used to identify the role orientations among ICT coordinators in primary schools of Andalucía (Spain). Three orientation clusters were identified: 'support to use ICT in the classroom' (67.1 %), 'promote ICT use in the classroom' (17.8 %), and 'planning and maintenance of ICT equipment in the school' (15.1 %). The interest in separating technician and pedagogical duties in two profiles and the perceived organizational support from the Teacher Centers were different in the three types of role orientation. Finally, strategies are suggested to reduce role ambiguity and role conflict in ICT Coordinators.

Keywords: ICT coordinator, role orientation, multidimensional scaling, role ambiguity, cluster analysis.

Building the role of ICT coordinators in primary schools. A typology based on task prioritization

1. Introduction

The last national report on the use of ICTs in Spanish schools *Plan Avanza* (2007; for more details, see <http://www.oei.es/tic/TICCD.pdf>) points out that almost all public primary schools (99 %) have ICT equipment and Internet access, but only half (54.2 %) of these schools have a project for the successful implementation of ICTs. In this regard, it is noteworthy that about half of primary schools use ICTs only during 30 % of school hours. Teachers use ICTs for managing personal work (29 %), surfing the Internet (42 %) and creating texts (55 %). Only one out of four students (26 %) uses the computer in the classroom every day or several times a week. In recent years, the average number of students per computer in public primary schools has decreased from 3.5 students in 2009-2010 to 3 students in 2014-2015 (MECD, 2017; for more details, see <https://www.mecd.gob.es/servicios-al-ciudadano-mecd/dms/mecd/servicios-al-ciudadano-mecd/estadisticas/educacion/indicadores-publicaciones-sintesis/datos-cifras/Datosycifras1718esp.pdf>). The regional education administrations –in our case the Education Administration in Andalusia– not are providing schools with computer equipment since no ICT education programs or policies on a national scale similar to the old *Programa Escuela 2.0* (for more details, see www.ite.educacion.es/escuela-20) are being offered.

On the other hand, the ICT coordinators from many countries such as the United States of America (Frazier & Bailey, 2004), Ireland (McGarr & McDonagh, 2013), Flanders -Belgium- (Devolder, Vanderlinde, van Braak, & Tondeur, 2010), New Zealand (Lai, & Pratt, 2004), Australia (Tondeur, Cooper, & Newhouse, 2010), and Singapore (Tay & Lim, 2016) are the professionals who manage how technological equipment is acquired. However, Spanish ICT coordinators are not allowed to carry out this task. We consider this may be due to the centralism

of Spanish education and its effects on the economic autonomy of schools (Luengo, Sevilla, & Torres, 2005).

The international papers and reports highlight the importance of the ICT coordinator's role when dynamizing the integration of ICTs in schools. Moreover, they point out that these professionals are more efficient when they have some knowledge of ICTs, use different strategies to promote their use among teachers and lead the educational change that the use of these technologies in schools brings about. Education authorities are aware of the important role developed by ICT Coordinators in schools. For this reason, they have been assigned a really relevant role in the ICT implementation process (Rodríguez-Miranda, Pozuelos-Estrada, & León-Jariego, 2014).

1.1. *Research into the role of ICT coordinators*

If we focus on the studies analyzing the functions and development of the ICT coordinator's role, very few studies have been conducted so far, especially when compared with other research topics of this area (e.g. educational technology, computer-mediated communication, virtual reality, etc.). A chronological study based on the use of "ICT coordinator" in different publications shows how this lack of attention is due to various factors. Firstly, this role is relatively new since it was created in the eighties when it was known as computer coordinator (Moursund, 1985). Secondly, different educational, technological and managerial requirements were assigned to ICT coordinators, what might have hindered the transparency of this role (Frazier, & Bailey, 2004). Thirdly, this role has not been studied homogeneously due to the different labels or names given to the same role, e.g.: Moursund (1992) identified it as technology coordinator, Buckley (1995) as technology facilitator, Strudler (1995) as school-based computer coordinator, Moallem and Micallef (1997) as technology resource teacher, Rath and Rieck (1997) as district computer coordinators, and Davidson (2003)

ICT coordinator's role

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3 as educational technologist. In the last decade, ICT coordinator has been identified as the most
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5 common expression related to this role (Devolder, Vanderlinde, van Braak, & Tondeur, 2010;
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7 Hadjithoma-Garstka, 2011; Lai, & Pratt, 2004; McGarr, & McDonagh, 2013; Tearle, 2003).
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10 Fourthly, ICT coordinators can work on a full-time basis (Davidson, 2003; Murphy, Allred, &
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12 Brescia, 2018) or be teachers with teaching responsibilities (Rodríguez-Miranda, Pozuelos-
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14 Estrada, & León-Jariego, 2014).
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17 In the Spanish region of Andalusia, this role was incorporated into schools in 2003, when
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19 the first ICT centers started to operate. Classrooms and management areas in ICT centers were
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21 equipped with the necessary hardware and software. They were also provided with fiber optic
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23 Internet access and a training program in ICTs for teachers. In order to be recognized as ICT
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25 centers, schools were required to submit an ICT project that had to be assessed by the Education
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27 Administration. The ICT project was developed by either a team of teachers sensitized to the use
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29 of ICTs in schools or directly by the management team of the school. The implementation of the
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31 ICT project was assigned to a teacher with initiative and educated in these technologies, who
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33 applied voluntarily for the said position and was endorsed by the staff meeting. The ICT
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35 coordinators share their teaching functions with those related to this new role which requires 5.25
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37 hours out of a total of 25 hours per week.
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42 The eight functions of ICT coordinators in Andalusia have been classified following the
43
44 ICT coordinator's role typology proposed by Devolder et al. (2010, p. 1964), can be found in
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46 table 1. In this context, ICT coordinators carry out different functions or roles: planners,
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48 educationalists, and technicians; however, other roles are not associated with them such as
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50 budgeters (manage ICT budget). In our opinion, the planner, educationalist, and technician roles
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52 (Devolder et al., 2010) coincide respectively with the three areas of activity of ICT coordinators
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54 (policy-making, walking-around, and nuts-and-bolts) identified by Marcovitz (2000). These three
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ICT coordinator's role

roles had already been described in a previous work carried out by Lynch, Hobbs, and Hollanders (1999). They identified and labeled the three work priorities of ICT coordinators as long and medium planning, training and encouraging staff, and sorting out hardware and software problems (see table 1).

Table 1

Template of roles and areas of the ICT coordinator's functions

Roles (Lynch et al., 1999)	Areas (Marcovitz, 2000)	Roles (Devolder et al., 2010)	Eight functions of ICT coordinators in Andalusian schools (Spain)
<i>Long and medium planning</i>	<i>Policy-making</i> Activities about school technology policy...in the way the school uses technology to enhance the learning environment	<i>Planner</i> Fulfillment of tasks related to the planning, the development, the facilitation, and the monitoring of an ICT-vision and an ICT-policy	Establishing means for the experience diffusion as well as information exchange with other schools. <i>Diffusion experience</i> Encouraging actions leading to the project's expansion and improvement. <i>Improvement Project</i> Administering school intranet and managing user' accounts. <i>Intranet management</i> Coordinating the elaboration and updating of the school website. <i>School website</i>
<i>Training and encouraging staff</i>	<i>Walking-around</i> Includes any support given by virtue of being in the right place at the right time	<i>Educationalist</i> Supporting teachers in the implementation of ICT in the classroom and training teachers in the area of ICT and its use in the classroom	Guiding school's teachers about the resources available on the Net and in the school contents' server. <i>Teaching assistant</i> Encouraging the development of educational contents by the teachers as well as their diffusion in the whole school community. <i>Promoting ICT contents</i> Managing educational tools and facilitating their use by teachers. <i>Management tools</i>
<i>Sorting out hardware and software problems</i>	<i>Nuts-and-bolts</i> Include tasks that require the expertise of a technician	<i>Technician</i> Taking responsibility for the management and maintenance of the ICT equipment and being available for communication concerning technical questions and problems	Guiding the teachers in problem-solving (technical...) that may appear during the project development. <i>Technical support</i>

Three studies that were carried out in different contexts and periods and with different methods in the United Kingdom (1999), the United States of America (2000), and Flanders, the Dutch-speaking part of Belgium (2010), identified a similar typology of the ICT coordinator's role. Along the same lines, Vanderlinde, Dexter, and van Braak (2012) also suggest that, apart from working as educationalists and technicians, ICT coordinators should focus their leadership on their role as planners since it is essential to effectively integrate ICTs in schools. This role typology associated with ICT coordinators is also shared by other researchers of the area and, as stated before, it also coincides with the functions assigned by the Education Administration to ICT coordinators in Andalusian schools.

1.2. *ICT coordinators as job crafters. The importance of examining their role orientation*

This institutionalized role definition does not guarantee that ICT coordinators adjust their role to the said functions. Three factors may hinder the adjustment of the assigned roles. Firstly, several functions, which have not been previously prioritized, are attached to the ICT coordinator's role and they must decide how they are prioritized. Secondly, many functions are new and no previous rules or criteria can be used by coordinators to orient their role. Thirdly, ICT coordinators should be creative and provide new work proposals to lead the changes derived from the use of ICTs in schools. Following the lines proposed by Jones (1986), this organizational context favors an individualized role orientation versus an institutionalized role orientation in ICT coordinators.

As stated by Davis and Wacker (1987), people create a global and proactive approach of their roles beyond the initial tasks assigned to their positions in order to feel responsible for their work. Even in a same job, employees perceive their role in a different way (Parker, 2007). For example, an ICT coordinator can define his role by feeling responsible for any help or petition needed that may not be established in the ICT project, such as designing activities to reduce

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3 digital divide in the students' families. On the contrary, other coordinators might define their jobs
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5 more narrowly and they can only feel responsible for certain traditional roles such as solving
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7 simple hardware problems. In this case, the reduction of the digital divide in the students'
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9 families would be seen as 'this is not my job'. According to Parker, Wall, and Jackson (1997)
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11 these coordinators do not perceive their role orientation in the same way.
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15 Wrzesniewski & Dutton (2001) identified technicians in computer-supported cooperative
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17 work as an example of job crafters. In our opinion, the characteristics of the ICT coordinator's
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19 role and the school's organizational context where they carry out their work also contribute to see
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21 ICT coordinators as job crafters.
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23 24 1.3. *The purpose of this study*

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26 Several works (Devolder et al., 2010; Marcovitz, 2000) have studied the characteristics of
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28 the ICT coordinator's role. So far, however, there has been little discussion about the differences
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30 in the role orientation of these coordinators. In this work, we will study the role orientation of
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32 ICT coordinators by analyzing how they individually prioritize their functions. According to
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34 Phelen (1960), cited in Rizzo, House, & Lirtzman (1970, p. 152), "in the presence of multiple and
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36 conflicting standards whose relative importance is undefined, subordinates must determine the
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38 priority of accomplishment". People begin to orient their roles by defining and reorganizing their
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40 functions in order to act in response to the meanings and priorities they have assigned to these
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42 functions (Rosenberg, 1978). The importance attributed to each task facilitates the role
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44 orientation hierarchy and reorganizes the role functions depending on the amount of time
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46 attributed to each task (Steele, 1991). As a result, when ICT coordinators follow their own
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48 criteria and decide to prioritize their functions, they start to create their own ICT coordinator's
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50 role.
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After determining the priority criteria that allow us to identify the ICT coordinators' role orientation, we will try to answer two research questions: 1) Is it possible to identify different types of ICT coordinators according to their role orientation? 2) What differences can be found between ICT coordinators depending on their role orientation typology? Answering the first question will help us determine how this role is being developed in practice. In line with the study on the teachers' role carried out by Becker and Riel (1999), we consider that the way ICT coordinators define their role will determine how they spend their limited time both in and outside the classroom. The second answer will allow us to identify the different types of ICT coordinators and also to discuss with stakeholders how their role can be adjusted to their functions.

2. Methods

2.1. Procedure

After accessing the census of all Andalusian primary schools with ICT projects, their ICT coordinators were contacted and informed about the study. They were then asked to contribute to this study by filling in an anonymous and confidential questionnaire. The questionnaire was sent via e-mail to 179 ICT coordinators working in the eight provinces of Andalusia. Three reminders were sent to participants to ensure that, at least, 50 % of participants had completed the questionnaire.

2.2. Participants

The research team received 101 questionnaires that had been completely filled in by the ICT coordinators. All ICT coordinators in Andalusia were teachers with teaching responsibilities. Since role orientation has been studied through a preference variable, those questionnaires containing missing values or errors in this core variable were removed from the study. In the end, a total of 73 questionnaires (72.6 % males) were analyzed. Around 1 out of 3 coordinators (31.5

ICT coordinator's role

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3 %) were under 40 years old. They had been teaching for an average of 19.96 years (SD = 8.65)
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5 and working as ICT coordinators for 2.1 years (SD = 0.9). ICT coordinators devoted an average
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7 of 5.25 hours per week to develop their functions that were simultaneously combined with their
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9 teaching responsibilities. In table 2 we can see more details about other professional
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11 characteristics of ICT coordinators and variables related to their role development.
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Table 2

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15 Sociodemographic characteristics and variables related to the development of the ICT
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17 coordinator's role

	n (%)
Gender	Male = 53 (72.6) Female = 20 (27.4)
Age	21-30 years old = 6 (8.2) 31-40 years old = 17 (23.3) 41-50 years old = 31 (42.5) + 50 years old = 19 (26)
Educational level	Graduate = 44 (60.3) Master = 29 (39.7)
Previous participation in teaching innovation projects	Yes = 46 (63) No = 27 (37)
Previous collaboration with the Computing Department of the Teacher Center to support ICT projects	Yes = 20 (27.4) No = 53 (72.6)
ICT coordinator role compatible with school management functions (Yes = 53)	Combined with school leadership positions = 34 (46.6) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Head teacher = 18 (24.7) • Secretary, Head of Studies = 16 (21.9) Combined with other responsibilities (non-leadership positions) such as coeducation coordinator, bilingual program coordinator, etc. = 19 (26)
Do you think, as ICT coordinator, that the temporary exemption is enough?	Yes = 10 (13.7) No = 63 (86.3)
Access to the role of ICT coordinator	Self proposed = 38 (52.1) Elected by the school board = 35 (47.9)
How do you value the ICT development project?	Positive = 59 (80.8) Indifferent = 4 (5.5) Negative = 10 (13.7)
According to the following characteristics, how do you think ICTs are being integrated in the curriculum in your school?	ICTs are commonly used in the classroom in the same way as other resources = 28 (40.6) ICTs are used in planned activities and in specific periods of time = 9 (13) ICTs are only used in conventional activities and no specific periods of time have been established for them = 32 (46.4)

ICT coordinator's role

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	Mean	Std Dev	Min	Max
Years of experience as a teacher	19.96	8.65	1	36
Years of experience as an ICT coordinator	2.07	.9	1	4
Self-perception of ICT training (hardware and software) ^a	2.86	.93	1	5
Self-perception of ICT training (teaching-learning) ^a	3.21	.97	1	5
I am very busy with my job as an ICT coordinator ^b	4.53	.58	3	5

^a(1 = very low training to 5 = very high training)

^b(1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree)

Around three out of four ICT coordinators combined their role as ICT coordinators with other managerial positions in their schools. Bearing in mind that international research has consistently found that the leadership of a school (principal and leadership team) is a critical factor in the way in which educational technologies such as computers are used in schools (see Newhouse, 2010), we analyzed the differences in the socio-demographic and professional profile and the priority given by ICT coordinators (with and without managerial positions in their schools) to their professional functions.

No significant differences were found in the socio-demographic (age and sex) and the professional profile (years of teaching experience, participation in ICT projects, etc.) of both types of ICT coordinators. However, a significant difference was observed regarding the priority given to professional functions: coordinators without managerial functions were more focused on facilitating the use of educational tools and how they should be managed by teachers. This is due to the fact that ICT coordinators with management experience have a general view of the center while those who do not carry out these functions tend to focus their work in the classroom.

2.3. Measures

A questionnaire based on the literature review was created to know what ICT coordinators thought about the implementation of ICTs in schools and the development of their own role in this process. The first version of this questionnaire was supervised by professors specialized in

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3 this area. After receiving their feedback, a new pilot version of the said questionnaire was used
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5 with four ICT coordinators in order to improve the comprehension of some items. Several socio-
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7 demographic variables and other variables related to the activity of ICT coordinators were
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9 included in the final version. In a second block, participants were asked about their teaching and
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11 coordinating experience, and if they held other managerial positions in their schools. They were
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13 also asked about their ICT training their involvement in teaching innovation projects and how
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15 they obtained their positions as ICT coordinators. Finally, they were asked to assess the ICT
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17 implementation experience in their schools and if they considered the time spent as ICT
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19 coordinators was enough. To study their role orientation, a preference variable was used based on
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21 the importance given by coordinators to each of the eight functions assigned by the Education
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23 Administration to this role. Participants were asked to rank the importance given to these eight
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25 functions (see table 1). The scale used ranged from 1 (the most important function) to 8 (the least
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27 important function).
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34 *2.4. Research methodology*

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36 Multidimensional scaling (MDS) was used to identify the criteria used by ICT
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38 coordinators when giving priority to their eight functions. MDS includes several techniques that
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40 contribute to identify key dimensions underlying respondents' evaluations of objects. Through
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42 the analysis of the spatial representation of behavioral data, MDS tries to identify non-observable
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44 factors that influence behavior (Kruskal, & Wish, 1978). In this study, the alternating least
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46 squares scaling (ALSCAL) algorithm was used. The ALSCAL solution showed a two-
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48 dimensional map in which functions were shown in accordance with the priorities given by ICT
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50 coordinators. The interpretation of these two dimensions helped us identify the criteria used by
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52 ICT coordinators to prioritize their tasks and how they orient their role. In order to calculate the
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1 ICT coordinator's role

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3 differences between respondents in their perception of the priorities given to their functions, the
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5 weighted Euclidean or individual differences scaling algorithm (INDSCAL) was used. The
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7 INDSCAL solution facilitated the coordinates of each subject in the two-dimensional map that
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10 can be used in subsequent analyses.

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12 The next step was to empirically identify the types of role orientation in ICT coordinators
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14 by applying a hierarchical cluster analysis (Ward method) of the individual coordinates in the
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16 perceptual map showing the priority assigned to tasks. Clustering techniques have already been
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18 used to identify profiles in the teacher educational beliefs (Tondeur, Hermans, van Braak, &
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20 Valcke, 2008). In our case, cluster analysis helped us understand how ICT coordinators can be
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22 grouped according to the criteria they use when prioritizing their duties. In this regard, since the
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24 Ward method maximizes inter-cluster differences and minimizes intra-cluster distances, cluster
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26 analysis results showed the different types of role orientation in ICT coordinators.
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30 Finally, discriminant analysis was used to examine differences in ICT coordinators
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32 according to their type of role orientation. Statistical analyses were performed with SPSS Version
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37 **3. Results**

38 *3.1. Multidimensional scaling of the priority given to functions*

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40 The ALSCAL algorithm was performed to graphically represent how participants
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42 perceive the priority of their tasks. Figure 1 shows the perceptual map of the multidimensional
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44 scaling (MDS) for a two-dimensional solution.
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Figure 1. Perceptual map of the priority given to functions. Derived stimulus configuration

This MDS solution was evaluated with two goodness-of-fit parameters: stress (the proportion of the variance of the disparities not accounted for by the MDS model) and RSQ (the proportion of the variance between the predicted and obtained distances in the configuration). In our model, a stress value of .017 and a RSQ value of .998 showed that the two-dimensional solution is acceptable. Following the recommendations given by Hair, Black, Babin, and Anderson (2010), two additional techniques were used for judging the adequacy of this MDS solution: the scree plot and the Shepard diagram. In the scree plot, the amount of stress is plotted against the number of dimensions. An “elbow” in the plot indicates that a greater number of dimensions in the MDS solution only contribute to a small reduction of stress. This “elbow” indicates the correct number of dimensions. S-stress values for one- to four-dimensional solutions were .044, .028, .020, and .017, respectively. The largest decrease in S-stress occurs when the

second dimension is added. The Shepard diagram, a scatter plot of linear fit, displays the relationship between points in the MDS plot against the observed dissimilarities. In MDS solution with a good fit, the points in the plot should adhere cleanly to a straight line. In our case, both graphs showed that a two-dimensional MDS solution allow us to identify the criteria used by ICT coordinators when prioritizing their functions.

In the perceptual map, we can see that promoting ICT contents, teaching assistant and management tools functions are situated in the negative pole of dimension 1, whereas diffusion experience, school website, technical support and intranet management functions are located in the opposite pole (see figure 1 and table 3). Based on this localization, we considered that dimension 1 reflects the context (classroom vs. whole school community) in which ICT coordinators develop their functions. On the left side of dimension 1, we find the functions that are generally developed in the classroom, whereas on the positive side we can find the functions aimed at the whole school community. In the center of dimension 1 (coordinate = .0004) we can find the improvement project, a function which, simultaneously, aims at the classroom and the whole school community. In dimension 2, the greatest negative distance corresponds to the technical support function, while the improvement project and diffusion experience functions are situated in the positive pole. Dimension 2 can indicate the complexity of the functions. The functions situated in the negative pole do not require previous programming and can be immediately and individually solved; due to their resemblance to the traditional activities carried out by teachers, are more well-known by ICT coordinators (e.g. management tools). Conversely, the functions situated in the positive pole require previous programming to be developed in the long term. Moreover, these functions involve the development of competences to contact and negotiate with other people, explain the ICT project and argue reasons in favor of their implementation. In addition, they are less frequent in the teacher's traditional work (e.g.

improvement project). For such reasons, we considered that the positive side of dimension 2 indicates a greater complexity of tasks (complex tasks), while the negative side reflects a lower level of difficulty (simple tasks).

Table 3

Coordinates of the eight functions in the two dimensions of multidimensional scaling (ALSCAL algorithm)

	Dimension	
	1	2
Technical support	.9602	-.9797
Diffusion experience	.9072	.8595
Improvement project	.0004	.7073
Intranet management	1.8027	-.0070
School website	.9799	-.0928
Teaching assistant	-1.6718	-.1842
Promote ICT contents	-1.7102	.3117
Management tools	-1.2683	-.6149

To validate the MDS results, calculations were repeated in two randomly selected subsamples consisted of approximately 50 % of subjects. In both cases, the two-dimensional solution showed adequate fit indices (subsample #1: Stress = .03013 and RSQ = .98109 / subsample #2: Stress = .01634 and RSQ = .99849). The strong correlations between dimension 1 ($r = .993$) and dimension 2 ($r = .898$) in both subsamples provided some internal validity to the MDS results. Subsequently, the INDSCAL procedure in SPSS was used. Separate dissimilarity matrixes for all 73 subjects were input into this program to calculate the coordinates of each ICT coordinator in the perceptual map.

3.2. Cluster analysis of individual coordinates in the perceptual map

A hierarchical cluster analysis (Ward method, squared Euclidean distance) was carried out in order to divide the perceptual space into subspaces composed of ICT coordinators that use similar criteria when prioritizing their functions. Both the agglomeration schedule and

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3 dendrogram were used to select an adequate cluster solution. Table 4 shows data from the
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5 agglomeration coefficient in the different cluster solutions. As expected, the agglomeration
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7 coefficient showed the greatest increases in going from step 69 to 72 (18.7 vs. 84.05). Although
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9 the greatest increase of the agglomeration coefficient was caused by combining two clusters into
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11 one, cluster solutions almost always show a large increase for this step (Hair et al., 2010). As a
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13 result, the significant increase of the coefficient (21.56) that occurs when going from 3 to 2
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15 clusters suggests a possible stopping point. The greatest increase in heterogeneity occurs when
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17 going from step 70 to 71, a result that favors a three-cluster solution over a two-cluster solution.
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19 This cluster solution was found when analyzing the scree plot. The dendrogram analysis shows
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21 that, at five rescaled distance, three clusters emerged (see figure 2). The two-cluster solution
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23 increases rescaled distance to 15, resulting in a cluster solution with a higher level of
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25 heterogeneity. As reflected in the agglomeration schedule, the dendrogram suggested that there
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27 were three different types of role orientation in ICT Coordinators.
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Table 4

Agglomeration Schedule of the cluster analysis of the INDSCAL coordinates

Step of the clustering procedure	No. of cluster after combining	Agglomeration Coefficient this step	Differences	Proportion increase in heterogeneity to next step
63	10	4.07	0.85	20.89
64	9	4.92	1.06	21.51
65	8	5.98	1.48	24.69
66	7	7.45	2.48	33.32
67	6	9.94	3.09	31.05
68	5	13.02	5.68	43.61
69	4	18.70	7.12	38.05
70	3	25.82	21.56	83.50
71	2	47.37	36.68	77.42
72	1	84.05		

review only

Note: The clusters have been numbered according to the agglomeration schedule

Figure 2. Dendrogram for cluster analysis (Ward method) of the ICT coordinators' coordinates in the perceptual map

Cluster 1, which was made up of 13 ICT coordinators, was situated in the 'classroom activities' negative pole of dimension 1 and in the 'complex tasks' positive pole of dimension 2. Cluster 2, which was the largest cluster ($n = 49$), was mainly situated in the 'classroom activities' negative pole of dimension 1 and in the 'simple tasks' negative pole of dimension 2. Finally, cluster 3, which was composed of 11 subjects, was mainly situated in the 'center tasks' and 'complex tasks' positive poles of both dimensions (see figure 3). The priority given to the ICT coordinator's role (Devolder's typology) was analyzed in each cluster to verify the difference between them. From the role types described in table 1, the planner, educationalist and technician variables were calculated. After that, an analysis of variance of the ICT coordinator's role was performed. In table 5 we can see that the differences between the three roles were significant between clusters. A post-hoc procedure (the Tukey HSD or Games-Howell test) was carried out when F value was significant. The planner role was more prioritized in clusters 1 and 3 and less prioritized in cluster 2. The educationalist role was more important for clusters 1 and 2 than for cluster 3. Finally, ICT coordinators of cluster 3 prioritized the technician role when compared with their colleagues from clusters 1 and 2. To validate the Ward cluster solution, the non-hierarchical cluster analysis (k-means method) was used (Punj, & Stewart, 1983). The k-means solution for $k = 3$ grouped 95.9 % of ICT coordinators in the same way as the Ward solution. Only subjects #38, #53 and #55 changed from cluster 3 to cluster 1 (see figure 3). The correspondence in size and profile of the clusters obtained with hierarchical and non-hierarchical solutions confirmed the role orientation typology suggested by us.

Note: ——— cluster 1 (n= 13);..... cluster 2 (n= 49);- - - - cluster 3 (n = 11)

Figure 3. Derived subject weights and results of hierarchical cluster analysis

Table 5

Analysis of variance of the role orientation in the clusters

Criteria used to prioritize functions	Cluster1 ^a (C1)	Cluster 2 (C2)	Cluster 3 (C3)	F	Sig.	Post-hoc comparison test ^b
Dimension 1 classroom (negative values) to center tasks (positive values) Minimum ^c = -.86. Maximum = 2.39	-.66 (.21)	-.24 (.39)	1.36 (.76)	77.11	.000	C1 < C2 < C3
Dimension 2 simple (negative values) to complex tasks (positive values) Minimum = -.97. Maximum = 1.85	.86 (.38)	-.52 (.28)	.80 (.86)	80.8	.000	C2 < C1 C2 < C3
Priority given to role (Devolder's tipology)^c						
Planner Minimum = 3.50. Maximum = 7.25	5.02 (.61)	5.91 (.59)	5.16 (.81)	14.19	.000	C1 < C2 C3 < C2
Educationalist Minimum = 1. Maximum = 6.33	2.79 (.96)	2.25 (.42)	4.58 (.91)	61.24	.000	C1 < C3 C2 < C3
Technician Minimum = 1. Maximum = 8	6.15 (1.52)	5.71 (2.05)	2.73 (1.95)	11.83	.000	C3 < C1 C3 < C2

^a Means (standard deviation); ^b Tukey HSD test was performed when equal variances are assumed. Games–Howell test was performed when equal variances could not be assumed. Only significant differences are shown. $p < .05$; ^c high values indicate low priority role.

3.3. Discriminant analysis of the three clusters

A previous exploratory analysis was carried out to select the variables that allow us to distinguish the different types of ICT coordinators according to their role orientation. Two variables were entered in the descriptive discriminant analysis: the need to separate two roles of the ICT coordinator (technician vs. pedagogical), and the institutional support perceived from the Education Administration. One significant discriminant function emerged (Wilks' $\lambda = .782$; $\chi^2(4) = 17.05$; $p = .002$; canonical $R^2 = .21$) that provided 68.5 % correct group classifications. After examining the structure coefficients (see table 6), we can see that the discriminant function is positively correlated with the two variables. The need to separate technician functions from pedagogical functions showed a higher correlation and higher standardized coefficient with discriminant function than the perceived organizational support.

Table 6

Standardized and structure coefficients for discriminant function

	Standardized coefficient	Structure coefficient
Separation of duties (technician vs. pedagogical)	.833	.921
Institutional support perceived from the Education Administration	.400	.583

4. Discussion

This article has studied the role orientation of ICT coordinators by analyzing the priority given by these teachers to their duties. The MDS solution suggests that coordinators use two criteria to prioritize their duties: the context in which they are performed (classroom - whole school community) and their level of complexity (easy task - complex task). In this study, the distance of each subject to the 'task complexity' dimension and the 'task context' dimension reflects a major aspect of their role orientation. A cluster analysis of these individual differences was carried out to study the role orientation typology. Three clusters were identified. The largest cluster was cluster 2 with 67.1 % of the coordinators who prioritized classroom activities and simple tasks. Cluster 1 was composed of 17.8 % of participants that prioritized classroom and complex tasks. Both clusters gave the maximum priority to the educationalist function. This means that around 85 % of ICT coordinators focused their role on developing ICT classroom activities. This high consensus in the educationalist role orientation may be due to its integrated functions (teaching assistant, promoting ICT contents, and management tools) that are more common in the teaching tasks that have been previously developed by ICT coordinators (Marcovitz, 2000). Although clusters 1 and 2 agree on the importance given to classroom activities, the ICT coordinators from cluster 1 prioritized complex tasks related to planner functions (management, improvement, and diffusion of the ICT project) when compared with

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3 ICT coordinators from cluster 2. Despite the fact that this difference has contributed to identify
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5 two specific types of role orientation, we would like to highlight that most of the coordinators (85
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7 %) gave more importance to the educationalist role when compared with the planner role, in line
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9 with the results reported by Devolder et al. (2010). Cluster 3 was the smallest cluster with only
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11 11 ICT coordinators (15.1 %) that prioritized center and complex tasks. The technician role was
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13 clearly prioritized in this cluster when compared with the educationalist and planner roles. ICT
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15 coordinators from cluster 3 showed a very different role orientation when compared with those
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17 from cluster 2. They showed significant differences in the five criteria used to analyze the ICT
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19 coordinators' role orientation. However, they shared with cluster 1 similar levels of priority
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21 assigned to complex tasks and the planner function.
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26 We believe that the cluster solution allows us to identify three types of role orientation in
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28 ICT coordinators. These three types are described in order as they appear in the cluster solution
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30 (see dendrogram, figure 2). The first type (17.8 %) gave the highest priority to the educationalist
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32 functions and, despite focusing their work in classroom tasks, complex tasks were prioritized.
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34 The first role orientation focuses on the educationalist functions related to the promotion and
35
36 improvement of the ICT project. We regard role orientation type 1 as 'promote ICT use in the
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38 classroom'. Around 2 out of 3 ICT coordinators represented the second type of role orientation.
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40 These coordinators also prioritized educational functions in the classroom; however, unlike the
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42 first type, they gave more priority to the development of simple tasks that were similar to their
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44 daily teacher activity. This role focuses on the support given to teachers for the use of ICTs in
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46 their daily teaching duty. We regard role orientation type 2 as 'support to use ICTs in the
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48 classroom'. The third type of role orientation (15.1 %) clearly focuses on the technician function.
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50 This was the only type of role orientation that prioritized the functions addressed to the whole
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ICT coordinator's role

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3 school over the classroom tasks. We have labeled this role orientation as 'planning and
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5 maintenance of ICT equipment in the school'.
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8 All this demonstrates that ICT coordinators tend to establish individualized pedagogical
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10 structures which do not share the common perspective of each school. In this sense, we consider
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12 that ICT coordinators should be educated so that they could work jointly with other members of
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14 the school administration and develop ICT projects based on a shared perspective ensuring future
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16 development at schools.
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19 The fact of having three different types of role orientation reveals a lack of shared vision
20
21 and reflects the ambiguity of the ICT coordinator's role. This role ambiguity may be related to
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23 the nature of the tasks carried out by these coordinators. In fact, the integration of ICTs in schools
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25 involves some important innovation and knowledge creation processes that are developed
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27 between the boundary spanner and the bounded school community. In this organizational context,
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29 ICT coordinators define their role by exchanging their knowledge and experiences with other
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31 members of the school community (see Wenger, 1998) and by adapting their perspectives to a
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33 complex educational context that may be hindering their role clarity.
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38 Two variables, the need to separate technician functions from pedagogical functions in the
39
40 ICT coordinator's duties and the perceived organizational support from the Teacher Centers
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42 (TCs), were different in the three types of role orientation.
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45 The results found in this work suggested a greater need to separate both functions in role
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47 orientation type 1 and 2 than in role orientation type 3 ('planning and maintenance of ICT
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49 equipment in the school'). This wish to separate technician and pedagogical functions may be
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51 indicating a role conflict in 9 out of 10 ICT coordinators who consider that both functions are
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53 incompatible. The ICT coordinators who took part in this study argued that they were very busy
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55 at work and that their education was more focused on teaching and less centered on technology
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ICT coordinator's role

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(see table 2). For these reasons, and as stated by Rizzo, House, and Lirtzman (1970), we consider that this is a person-role conflict or intrarole conflict caused by different conflicts between the time, resources, or capabilities of the focal person and defined role behavior.

The second variable of the discriminant function represented the organizational support perceived by the coordinators from the TCs. These centers represent a district-level organization that stimulates school-level improvement by promoting educational innovation activities and the integration of ICTs in schools (Fernández-Sierra, & Barquín-Ruiz, 2002). Role orientation type 3 received the lowest level of support from the TCs. As pointed out by Rhoades, and Eisenberg (2002), high perceived organizational support prevents workers' role ambiguity. In this study, the support received from the TCs was higher in the clusters with lowest levels of heterogeneity (role orientations 1 and 2). Clusters created at high distance show heterogeneity and differences between the members of the cluster. Greater distances between the members of the cluster can reflect the difficulty of establishing a clear role and, consequently, contribute to increase the cluster role ambiguity. This approach explains why cluster or role orientation 3, which received the lowest level of support from the TCs, showed also a higher level of heterogeneity or role ambiguity.

This study has three limitations. The first one (previously discussed) was the higher probability of making a type II or false-negative error due to a small sample size study ($n = 73$). Nevertheless, we would like to highlight that, although the response rate only reached 40.8 %, the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants in this study were similar to those of the whole group of ICT coordinators working in Andalusian primary schools. The second limitation was that no previous theory about the development of the ICT coordinators' role has been reported. This has hindered the selection of the discriminant variables of different role orientations. To face up this limitation, an exploratory analysis was performed to assess the

discriminant power from a wide range of variables that can be consulted in table 2. The third limitation refers to the identification of underlying dimensions of the perceptual map provided by the MDS solution. We thought that, although subjective procedures are possible (see Hair et al., 2010), future researches should include variables about the objective attributes of the ICT coordinator's role (e.g. item "Indicate the level of difficulty of diffusion of the ICT project function. Easy = 1 to difficult = 5"). This additional information will contribute to use an objective procedure by identifying underlying dimensions of priority given to functions (e.g. Profit method). We also suggest using questionnaires to assess the ICT coordinator's role orientation similar to the Professional Role Orientation Inventory (Bebeau, Born, & Ozar, 1993).

5. Conclusions

Investing money and developing the technology available in schools are not enough if a full integration of ICTs is wanted. In fact, it is essential that stakeholders of the school community are involved in this process so that a real integration can be reached. To ensure that the whole school community takes part, we must reduce any resistance to change perceived in the implementation of ICTs. The Education Administration decided to include a new role to manage this process and this is how the ICT coordinator's role was created. However, they carry out several tasks and have to deal with many unpredictable questions from teachers, what hinders the clarity of their role.

The consolidation of a certain role requires that teachers show a shared vision of their tasks and duties. Nevertheless, the results found in this research showed three types of role orientation based on the priority given by each coordinator to their duties. In our opinion, these findings reveal that ICT coordinators and role ambiguity are hand in hand and, therefore, a more accurate attention should be paid by the Education Administration.

We think that several strategies should be developed to reduce the said ambiguity and promote a shared vision of their own role:

- Discussing with stakeholders about the criteria used to prioritize their duties.
- Promoting the implementation of ICT projects including the main objectives for a successful implementation of ICT in schools, its timing and the human resources necessary for its development.
- Building teams of ICT coordinators at schools versus a single professional.
- Giving more support to TCs and developing new training opportunities to improve ICT coordinators' planning skills.

On the other hand, some researchers (Marcovitz, 2000; McGarr, & McDonagh, 2013) agree on the idea that ICT coordinators should support their colleagues on technical and pedagogical issues. However, most of the participants in this study consider that these functions should be assigned to two different professional profiles. The need to separate technological from pedagogical functions involves a role conflict for ICT coordinators. We believe that this discrepancy is an important topic in the ICT coordinator's role building to which the educational administration also should pay attention.

To effectively face up the complex organizational processes to integrate ICT in schools, ICT coordinators need to develop a clear professional identity. In this sense, we consider that this paper has contributed to this target.

Statements on open data, ethics and conflict of interest

All ICT coordinators were informed about the purpose of the study. The information was collected anonymously and its processing was strictly confidential.

Data are available upon request. For more information can be contacted at leon@uhu.es.

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Running head: BUILDING THE ROLE OF ICT COORDINATORS

Building the role of ICT coordinators in primary schools. A typology based on task prioritization

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Keywords: ICT coordinator, role orientation, multidimensional scaling, Primary education, Quantitative Analysis.

Short Abstract

Analysis of the priority given by coordinators to their different functions and a subsequent cluster analysis were used to identify the role orientations among ICT coordinators. Three orientation clusters were identified: 'support to use ICT in the classroom' (67.1 %), 'promote ICT use in the classroom' (17.8 %), and 'planning and maintenance of ICT equipment in the school' (15.1 %). The interest in separating technician and pedagogical duties in two profiles and the perceived organizational support from the Teacher Centers were different in the three types of role orientation. Finally, strategies are suggested to reduce role ambiguity in ICT Coordinators

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